

ECOLOGICAL PROBLEMS OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The transition to a green economy is becoming one of the priorities in many countries around the world. The goal of the "green economy" is economic growth, which is possible through public and private investment in "green sectors" of the economy and the development of "green skills" among entrepreneurs and businesses. The article examines the development of green finance in Central Asian countries.*

Keywords: *green finance, air pollution, energy efficiency of production, environmental safety, business activities, risk management, environmental factors.*

Introduction. Uzbekistan is a country significantly affected by climate change. The country's average annual temperatures are rising and are expected to continue increasing. Climate change and extreme weather events have led to longer periods of dry heat, reduced snow accumulation, glacier degradation, increased evaporation in plains and foothills, more frequent droughts, and extreme low-water events. It is expected that weather conditions in the country will become even hotter and drier. More frequent and intense periods of abnormal heat, droughts, and changes in precipitation patterns will lead to an increase in extreme weather events such as heavy rains, floods, and mudslides. Climate change exacerbates land degradation and desertification, thereby affecting agricultural production and biodiversity.

The significant population and economic growth in Uzbekistan is one of the main drivers of socio-economic and environmental changes. The nationwide project "Yashil Makon" (Green Space) has been developed in the republic. As part of this project, 138 million trees were planted during the spring season of 2024 (110.5% of the plan). The Ministry of Ecology and local authorities have established 257 green parks in the regions, bringing the total number to 517. By the end of the current year, 75 million tree and shrub saplings will be planted as part of the autumn planting season of the "Yashil Makon" project. During this campaign, 134 green gardens will be created across the country.

By the end of 2024, green cover will be established on 300,000 hectares in the Aral Sea region, 200,000 hectares in Karakalpakstan, 50,000 hectares in Navoi region, 40,000 hectares in Bukhara region, and 10,000 hectares in Khorezm region. Additionally, during this period, 10 million tree saplings will be planted, and green belts will be created around enterprises categorized as having the highest environmental impact. In the past six months, 37 enterprises in the republic have built or reconstructed local wastewater treatment facilities. The Ministry of Ecology, together with the General Prosecutor's Office, has taken action against 44 enterprises discharging excessively polluted substances into Tashkent's "Salar," "Bektemir," and "Bozsuv" canals, with 12 enterprises disconnected from the sewer system.

Methodology. A cross-agency electronic information exchange system has been created in collaboration with the Academy of Sciences to determine the annual population of wild animals migrating through border areas with neighboring countries, and a list of these species has been compiled. Water protection zones have been established for 13 natural water bodies, including coastal areas. A state registry and inventory of economically significant animals in Bukhara and Jizzakh regions, as well as promising raw material enterprises in Namangan, Fergana, and Andijan regions, are being created. The species composition of flora in protected natural areas in these regions is also being inventoried.

In the Lower Amudarya State Biosphere Reserve, two electric pumps have been commissioned to halt forest degradation by drawing water from the Amu Darya River. On irrigated lands of Uzbekistan's Forest Fund, 1,000 hectares of fast-growing tree plantations and 500 hectares of protective tree plantations will be established. Additionally, 3,500 hectares of unused lands will be developed, increasing the country's forest cover to 8.1% (3.65 million hectares).

To prevent desertification, sand migration, water, and soil erosion, and to improve the environmental situation in desert, mountainous, and foothill areas, protective forests will be planted on 2,400 hectares. By the end of the current year, the accuracy of meteorological forecasts will be improved through the establishment of the "Takhtagoracha" station in Kashkadarya region and the implementation of a modern automated monitoring system.

In nine regions of the republic, 35 hydrological observation points will be equipped to enable online monitoring of water resources, improve early warning systems for floods and heavy rainfall, and track surface water levels nationwide. The installation of meteorological radar equipment in Surkhandarya region will allow full coverage of Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions, providing forecasts of hazardous hydrometeorological phenomena in mountainous and foothill areas and identifying high-risk zones.

The development of energy infrastructure has not kept pace with the rate of industrialization and urbanization driven by population growth. In Uzbekistan, the average annual water consumption in agriculture and industries such as cotton, textile, light manufacturing, food production, chemicals, and metallurgy remains high. Water shortages are worsening due to climate change, which increases the frequency and duration of droughts. Population growth is expected to further increase the demand for quality drinking water. Water pollution (both surface and groundwater) results from the inefficiency of wastewater treatment infrastructure. The main polluters are industrial, agricultural, and municipal enterprises. Efforts are underway to implement technologies that reduce water consumption, promote renewable energy use and recycling, and offer sustainable solutions for urban and rural populations.

Air pollution from both stationary and mobile sources is exacerbated by unfavorable climatic conditions. It is largely caused by key industries such as energy, oil and gas, metallurgy, chemicals, and construction, as well as the growing number of vehicles. However, in most observed cities, the average annual concentrations of major pollutants remain below the maximum permissible limits. Emissions of carbon monoxide and hydrocarbons have decreased, but emissions of nitrogen oxides and particulate matter have increased. The energy (76%) and agricultural (18%) sectors contribute the most to emissions.

In Uzbekistan, both negative and positive trends are observed in land management. Desertification is increasing due to both natural and human activities. However, positive trends include measures to expand green spaces, reduce land allocated for cotton, and increase areas for

vegetables, grains, fruits, and forage crops. There is also greater state support for water-saving irrigation technologies.

One of the causes of land degradation and desertification is excessive water use. Inefficient irrigation practices and outdated water supply infrastructure, which require large-scale reconstruction, have led to the rapid desertification and drying of the Aral Sea. Once one of the world's largest inland seas, the Aral has drastically shrunk due to large-scale irrigation projects diverting water from its tributaries. This ecological catastrophe has resulted in biodiversity loss, reduced fish stocks, and negative impacts on local communities.

Water issues in Uzbekistan are multifaceted, arising from a combination of geographical, climatic, economic, and governance factors. The country's arid and semi-arid climate, combined with limited water resources, presents serious challenges for sustainable water management. As a landlocked country in Central Asia, Uzbekistan faces chronic water shortages.

The scarcity of water resources is exacerbated by vast desert areas and shared water basins with neighboring countries. Agriculture is a key sector of the national economy, but it relies heavily on irrigation. The use of inefficient irrigation methods, outdated infrastructure, and poor technology results in excessive water consumption, leading to waste and depletion. The lack of integrated water resource management causes uneven distribution and overexploitation.

Industrial discharges, agricultural runoff, and inadequate wastewater treatment have led to water pollution, affecting both surface and groundwater. This pollution poses risks to both human health and the environment. Uzbekistan is vulnerable to climate change impacts, including shifts in precipitation patterns, rising temperatures, and glacier melting in the upper river basins. These changes could further deteriorate water availability and worsen existing water-related issues.

An analysis of the current state of protected natural areas in Uzbekistan and recent trends in this domain indicates that in recent years, both the number and total area of protected territories in the country have been expanding. Reforms in the forestry sector have led to a noticeable increase in forested lands. However, the negative impact of anthropogenic factors—such as land conversion for agricultural use, redistribution of surface water flow, extensive livestock grazing, energy development, and mining—remains persistent or is even intensifying. In mountainous regions, infrastructure expansion and population growth further exacerbate environmental pressures.

According to the target indicators of Uzbekistan's 2019–2030 Strategy for Transition to a Green Economy, the country aims to reduce greenhouse gas emissions per unit of GDP by 10% compared to 2010 levels and double energy efficiency while cutting carbon intensity. Additionally, the share of renewable energy sources in total electricity generation is set to reach 25%³³³. Ensuring universal access to modern, affordable, and reliable energy is a priority, alongside the modernization of industrial infrastructure to enhance sustainability through energy efficiency improvements and the adoption of cleaner, environmentally safe technologies—by at least 20%.

A key focus in Uzbekistan's green economy transition is the efficient use of water resources. Plans include the implementation of drip irrigation on up to 1 million hectares, increasing crop yields by 20–40%. The production of staple agricultural goods will rely on raising average productivity levels by 20–25%.

Diversification of energy consumption and the development of renewable energy sources are crucial in this transition. Meanwhile, the Uzbek government is actively addressing climate change adaptation, resource efficiency, and ecosystem conservation. Its green economy strategy aims to develop economic mechanisms to support green growth, strengthen institutional

frameworks for green technology adoption, enhance legal and regulatory frameworks, and integrate green economy principles into education and science. The strategy also focuses on improving industrial capacity and fostering a supportive environment for the green transition 333.

The Kyrgyz government has also prioritized the transition to a green economy. For example, the "Monitoring and Assessment Matrix for Kyrgyzstan's Transition to Sustainable Development" promotes economic growth while ensuring the conservation of natural assets. The matrix includes indicators evaluating resource efficiency, waste management, and air quality. It also assesses the extent of natural resource consumption and its environmental impact.

Furthermore, the environmental quality of life in Kyrgyzstan is measured through indicators reflecting the availability of basic infrastructure (e.g., sewage systems and drinking water) and their influence on public health. Economic indicators in the matrix cover revenues from environmental taxes, eco-tourism, and the sale of environmental goods and services.

The matrix comprises 65 green growth indicators, offering a comprehensive assessment of social, economic, and environmental factors. Kyrgyzstan has made a strategic decision to align itself with nations that embrace green economy principles. The country's indicators provide a clear picture of its green economy progress and overall environmental status.

Kyrgyzstan has been actively developing its national legislative framework for green growth and sustainable development. This legal foundation defines green economy goals, priority areas, and key concepts, while also establishing a system for monitoring and evaluating progress. The legislative framework encourages phasing out ozone-depleting substances, promoting organic farming, increasing the use of low-carbon and renewable energy sources, advancing solar and wind energy development, and transitioning to eco-friendly transport solutions 444.

An analysis of Kyrgyzstan's environmental and green growth indicators shows that 19 out of nearly 40 key indicators demonstrate positive trends, while another 19 exhibit negative dynamics. Moreover, it has been observed that Kyrgyzstan's National Statistics Committee does not publish the country's standing in the Environmental Performance Index (EPI)—a major international ranking. As of 2022, Kyrgyzstan ranked 126th out of 180 countries and held the lowest position among CIS nations.

Results and discussion. Despite these challenges, the approved Monitoring and Assessment Matrix has created opportunities for regional green growth by offering insights into resource efficiency and waste management in economic activities. Kazakhstan has adopted the "Kazakhstan-2050" Strategy, which outlines a long-term vision for building a resilient and efficient economy based on green development principles. The green economy is defined as an economic model that ensures a high quality of life, responsible and sustainable resource use, and the preservation of natural assets for future generations.

The transition to a green economy will enable Kazakhstan to achieve its goal of becoming one of the 30 most developed countries in the world. By 2050, the implementation of green economy initiatives is expected to: increase Kazakhstan's GDP by an additional 3%, Create over 500,000 new jobs, develop new industrial sectors and service industries, ensure high living standards across the country. The total investment required for this transition is estimated at 1% of GDP annually, which equates to \$3–4 billion per year. Rationale for Kazakhstan's green growth strategy Kazakhstan's shift towards a green economic model is highly relevant due to several key factors: infrastructure Renewal & Development, over the next 20 years, Kazakhstan will undergo a major infrastructure overhaul: by 2030, 55% of buildings and 40% of power plants will be newly

constructed. More than 80% of the vehicle fleet will be replaced with modern, energy-efficient models. This presents a unique opportunity to build a resource-efficient infrastructure.

Without proactive economic measures, Kazakhstan risks facing outdated and uncompetitive infrastructure in the near future. Growing Competitiveness of Green Technologies: green technologies are becoming increasingly cost-effective. Many alternative energy sources will soon surpass traditional energy sources in terms of cost efficiency.

Key Goals of the Kazakhstan-2050 Strategy Energy Sector: increase the share of alternative and renewable electricity to 50% by 2050. Improve energy efficiency by reducing the energy intensity of GDP.

Water Resources: ensure universal access to drinking water and provide sustainable water supplies for agriculture by 2040.

Agriculture: Increase agricultural land productivity by 1.5 times by 2020. Achieving these goals will require significant economic adjustments, allowing Kazakhstan to restore its water and land resources by 2030.

This will bring the country closer to OECD nations in terms of natural resource efficiency. Framework for the Green Economy Transition Kazakhstan's green economy concept outlines: air pollution, prevention measures, waste management policies, sustainable agricultural practices, water resource conservation, energy efficiency improvements, support for vulnerable social groups, creation of high-skilled jobs. Role of Government Policy a well-structured state environmental policy is a crucial factor in Kazakhstan's green economy transition. The regulatory framework ensures: state-backed renewable energy production and consumption, industrial modernization to reduce environmental pollution, enhanced energy efficiency in housing, utilities, and transport infrastructure.

The Kazakh government supports green projects through, tax incentives for green technologies, subsidized purchases of renewable electricity, financial support for waste recycling initiatives. Institutional Support research findings indicate that Kazakhstan has established a broad institutional framework to support green economy development, involving multiple authorized organizations across different government bodies.

Conclusion. Based on the analyzed environmental situations in the Central Asian countries, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- A green economy is an economic model that ensures sustainable economic growth with zero carbon emissions.
- The environmental and social costs of the current economic model in Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, and Kazakhstan are becoming increasingly evident. This highlights the need for new sources of growth that are environmentally sustainable, such as rapidly growing industries like renewable energy.

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